

NEW TREATMENT OPPORTUNITIES FOR ALLERGIC BRONCHITIS IN CHILDREN

A.I. Ulugov¹, D.M. Yunusov²

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute¹

Andijan State Medical Institute²

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15071977>

Abstract. *The given article presents an analysis of new possibilities for treating allergic bronchitis in children. Currently, leukotriene antagonists are the most effective treatment for allergic bronchitis in children. Leukotrienes (5-lipoxygenase inhibitors and leukotriene receptor antagonists) are anti-inflammatory drugs that may have fewer side effects compared to inhaled corticosteroids. The author presents research involving 63 patients aged 2 to 10 years who underwent treatment in the pulmonology department of the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute from 2021 to 2022. The obtained results showed that the inclusion of leukotriene antagonists in the complex treatment of allergic bronchitis significantly reduced the severity of bronchial obstruction syndrome, decreased coughing, and improved the general condition of patients. This confirms the appropriateness of using this group of drugs in pediatric practice for controlling the symptoms of allergic bronchitis and preventing its complications.*

Keywords: *allergic bronchitis, allergen contact, cough, leukotriene antagonists, children.*

Relevance. It is important to suggest that allergic bronchitis in children is quite common. This disease is widespread, with about 150-200 children out of every 1000 affected annually. The disease arises due to an inflammatory process in the bronchial mucosa. The disease begins when substances perceived by the body as foreign enter the respiratory system. The immune system responds to these foreign substances by narrowing the bronchial lumen and causing inflammation of the mucous membrane, resulting in spasms. Risk factors for the development of allergic bronchitis in children include genetic predisposition (if parents had similar issues), early childhood age, atopic constitution, living in an environmentally polluted area, or contact with allergens [1,2,4,6,7].

Definitely, the main symptom of the inflammatory process in the lungs is paroxysmal coughing. Attacks can occur at any time of the day, and they become more intense with exposure to triggering factors. Initially, the cough is dry, but after a while, thick mucus is produced. Breathing becomes difficult for the child, and shortness of breath develops. Due to bronchial spasms, breathing becomes shallow, inefficient, and frequent, accompanied by wheezing and crackling sounds. The child complains of a scratchy throat, discomfort, and itching in the nose [1,2,3,5,8].

Certainly, the child appears tired, becomes irritable, and their general condition is depressed. The temperature can rise up to 38°C, sweating increases, and weakness develops. Sometimes rashes appear on the skin, and there is inflammation of the mucous membranes of the nose, eyes, and paleness. Physical activity decreases: Children may avoid physical exertion due to shortness of breath and other symptoms.

Besides that, pathogenesis of allergic bronchitis in children involves a complex set of mechanisms related to the immune system and the respiratory system's response to allergens. In

allergic bronchitis, the child's immune system reacts to inhaled allergens as if they were dangerous to the body, even though they are harmless. This leads to the activation of various immune cells, including T-lymphocytes and eosinophils.

However, the response to allergens causes inflammation in the airways. This manifests as increased permeability of the bronchial mucosa, activation of eosinophils, the release of cytokines (such as interleukins and interferons), and other inflammatory mediators. Under the influence of allergens, bronchial lumens narrow, leading to impaired airflow and the development of characteristic symptoms such as coughing, shortness of breath, and wheezing. Repeated episodes of inflammation and bronchospasm can lead to remodeling of the bronchial walls, which is accompanied by changes in their structure and function. As a result of inflammation and remodeling, the bronchial walls become more sensitive to various irritants, leading to bronchial hyperreactivity.

Additionally, these mechanisms together form the pathogenesis of allergic bronchitis in children, which typically leads to characteristic clinical manifestations and complications such as a decline in quality of life, frequent respiratory infections, and airways obstruction syndrome [7,8,9,10,11,12].

The use of leukotriene antagonists includes:

- Fewer side effects: Unlike some other medications, leukotriene antagonists are usually well tolerated and can even be used in young children;
- Prevention of attacks: They help prevent attacks of allergic bronchitis, especially when used regularly;
- Complementary to other types of medications: They can be used in combination with other drugs, such as glucocorticosteroids and bronchodilators, to achieve maximum effect;
- Supported by clinical studies: Numerous clinical studies confirm the effectiveness of leukotriene antagonists in treating allergic bronchitis in children [9,10,11,12].
- The promising prospects of using leukotriene antagonists in pediatrics are due to their ability to control inflammation in the airways and prevent attacks of the disease, significantly improving the quality of life for children with allergic bronchitis. However, the decision to prescribe a specific medication should always be made by a doctor, taking into account the individual characteristics of the patient and the nature of the disease.
- The aim of the study was to investigate the clinical and laboratory effectiveness of the leukotriene antagonist drug, Breezesi (montelukast), in children with allergic bronchitis.

Material and Methods. From October 2021 to July 2022, we observed 63 patients suffering from allergic bronchitis. Among them, there were 27 girls and 36 boys aged from 2 to 10 years. Boys accounted for 57.14%, and girls for 42.8%. Children aged 2 to 3 years comprised 16 (25.4%), 4 to 6 years – 25 (39.6%), and 7 to 10 years – 22 (34.92%). The diagnosis of allergic bronchitis was most commonly made in children aged 4–10 years, constituting 74.5% of the cases.

Results and Discussion. While distributing patients by gender, it was noted that complicated cases of allergic bronchitis and upper respiratory tract diseases were more common in boys ($n = 57.14\%$), which is also consistent with the literature. An analysis of the medical history revealed unfavorable allergy-related heredity in 46.3% (29) of the children: among them, 14 (22.2%) had a family history of allergy on the mother's side, 9 (14.2%) on the father's side, and in 6 (9.5%) cases, both parents had allergic pathology. Additionally, 23 (36.5%) of the patients had a history of seasonal allergic rhinitis.

The primary diagnosis for all the children was allergic bronchitis. In addition, 23 patients also had allergic rhinitis, 3 had allergic tracheitis, 1 had atopic dermatitis, and 2 had allergic eczema.

The children were divided into two groups. Treatment for patients with allergic bronchitis should be comprehensive and individualized, taking into account the specifics of the disease course and the nature of sensitization in each child.

In the 1st (main) group, as part of the comprehensive treatment, all children received the antihistamine drug Breezesi (4.0 mg for children aged 2 to 4 years, and 5 mg for children aged 5 to 10 years) for 2 weeks. In the 2nd group (comparison), the antihistamine drug was cetirizine, which was administered at 2.5 mg for children aged 2 to 4 years, and 5 mg for children aged 5 to 10 years per day.

The diagnosis of allergic bronchitis was based on patient complaints, medical history, pulmonological examination, functional assessment of the nasal mucosa, paraclinical examination data, and consultations with pediatricians, allergists, and pulmonologists. Medical history also helps identify risk factors and disease triggers.

Additionally, the patient groups were comparable in terms of gender, age, disease severity, duration, and the intensity of clinical and functional symptoms of allergic bronchitis. All children underwent blood tests for eosinophils and serum testing for immunoglobulin E (IgE) before and after treatment. Before treatment, all patients were bothered by persistent and intrusive daytime and mainly nighttime coughing, with a normal body temperature. In 14.3% of the cases, patients were incorrectly diagnosed, and treatment was mistakenly prescribed. Children who also had allergic rhinitis experienced nasal congestion, sneezing attacks, rhinorrhea, and itching of the nasal mucosa (Table 1).

Definitely, in children with allergic bronchitis (AB), 77.8% (49) more frequently had dry, paroxysmal coughing ($p < 0.05$) (Table 1). The duration of the cough in the overall group of AB patients was 25.6 ± 6.0 days, and the cough had distinctive features. In 41/65.07%, rhinorrhea (watery, mucous nasal discharge, mucus dripping down the back of the throat) was observed, nasal congestion was present in 74.6%, itching of the nasal mucosa was seen in 57.1%, sneezing occurred in 46.03%, and in 12/19.04%, skin allergic reactions were noted, including 17.4% with edema, urticaria, and 22.2% with conjunctivitis. According to parents, many children with AB experienced sleep disturbances (39.7%) and reduced daily activity (46.03%).

Table № 1

Complaints in Observed Patients

Complaints	1st Group and 2nd Group
Cough	63/100%
Dry	49/77,8%
Wet, low productive	11/17,5%
Wet, productive	3/4,8%
Difficulty in nasal breathing	74,6%
Rhinorrhea	57,1%
Decreased daily activity	46,03%
Sneezing	46,03%
Urticaria and conjunctivitis	17,4%
Sleep disturbances	39,7%

According to allergological examination data, 32/50.8% of children with allergic bronchitis (AB) showed elevated levels of total IgE in their serum (91.67 IU/ml), with six patients having levels exceeding 1000 IU/ml. Eosinophilia in peripheral blood reached high levels (8-23%) and was persistent, while in the 2nd group, it was 20% ($p > 0.05$). After the completion of the 2-week treatment course with antihistamines, symptoms of allergic bronchitis decreased in both groups. No deterioration was observed in either group.

However, in the main group (Breezesi), the effect was achieved in all patients, and full remission and significant improvement were observed more frequently than in the comparison group (cetirizine).

The clinical picture was confirmed by laboratory examination results. Thus, eosinophil levels in all children from the 1st group decreased to normal values, while in 2 children from the comparison group, they remained above 5%. In 7 children from the 2nd group (cetirizine), IgE levels remained approximately the same as before treatment. Meanwhile, in all children from the 1st group (Breezesi), IgE levels decreased by almost 1.5-2 times. Only 4 (6.34%) children had a decrease in IgE levels within the range of 30.31 IU/ml. After the first course, 52/82.5% of patients noted significant relief, a reduction in the frequency of main complaints, and a decrease in the severity of objective clinical symptoms of the disease.

Conclusions:

Allergic bronchitis in children is a chronic condition that requires ongoing management and attention from both parents and healthcare professionals. Timely diagnosis and treatment can significantly improve the quality of life for the child and prevent complications.

While using Breezesi for the treatment of allergic bronchitis in children, it is important to follow the doctor's recommendations regarding dosage and frequency of administration. Additionally, individual characteristics of each child and their response to the medication should be considered.

REFERENCES

1. Ismatova K., Ulygov A. Experience of studying the anti-allergic effectiveness of the drug—brizezi in young children // development and innovations in science. – 2024. – Vol. 3. –N. 4. – Pp. 51-54.
2. Ismatova, Z., & Ismatova, K. (2024). Orbital and intracranial complications of rhinosinusitis in children. Today's scientific research in the eyes of youth, 2(2), Pp.22-23. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/research-in-eyes-youth/article/view/47725>
3. Nigmatzyanova Galiya Ilgamovna, Abdulina Alina Salavatovna, Galieva Elena Rustamovna, Kashuba Victoria Alexandrovna. Risk factors for the development and course of acute obstructive bronchitis in early childhood // Academy. 2020. N. 1 (52).
4. Mizerentsky Yu. L., Sulaymanov Sh. A. Antileukotriene drugs in modern pediatric practice // Russian journal of perinatology and pediatrics. – 2019. – Vol. 64. – No. 4. – Pp. 128-132.
5. Novik G. A. The role and place of antileukotriene drugs in the treatment of allergic diseases // The treating doctor. – 2014. – Vol. 3. – Pp. 75-82.
6. Yong Chen, Tingting Feng, Yong Li, Bin Du & Weiyu Weng. (2017) Formulation and evaluation of a montelukast sodium orally disintegrating tablet with a similar dissolution profile as the marketed product. Pharmaceutical Development and Technology 22:2, Pp. 168-172.

7. Diamant, Zuzana, Eva Mantzouranis, and Leif Bjermer. "Montelukast in the treatment of asthma and beyond." *Expert Review of Clinical Immunology* 5.6 (2009): Pp.639-658.
8. Liu, Fang, et al. "Leukotriene inhibitors for bronchiolitis in infants and young children." *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* 3 (2015).
9. Szeffler, Stanley J., and Eric AF Simoes. "Montelukast for respiratory syncytial virus bronchiolitis: significant effect or provocative findings?." *American journal of respiratory and critical care medicine* 167.3 (2003): Pp.290-291.
10. <https://www.krasotaimedicina.ru/diseases/allergic/allergic-bronchitis>
11. Waldbott, Geo L. "Allergic bronchitis." *The Journal of Laboratory and Clinical Medicine* 13.10 (1928): Pp.943-949.
12. Eder, C., et al. "Allergen-specific Ige levels against crude mould and storage mite extracts and recombinant mould allergens in sera from horses affected with chronic bronchitis." *Veterinary Immunology and Immunopathology* 73. 3-4 (2000): Pp.241-253.